

TEMPLATE:
IMPACT & ENGAGEMENT
STUDY

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TEMPLATE: IMPACT AND ENGAGEMENT STUDY

1. OVERVIEW

1.1 TITLE OF IMPACT AND ENGAGEMENT STUDY

1.2 LUDWIG BOLTZMANN INSTITUTE

1.3 PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATORS; RESEARCH TEAM MEMBERS

1.4 ABSTRACT FOR THE GENERAL COMMUNITY (MAXIMUM 250 WORDS)

1.5 KEYWORDS

1.6 SCIENTIFIC DISCIPLINES (CODE STATISTICS AUSTRIA)

1.7 SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS RELEVANT TO THE IMPACT (UNITED NATIONS)

1.8 USERS AND BENEFICIARIES

1.9 PARTNERS

1.10 FUNDERS

2. IMPACT¹ AND ENGAGEMENT² STUDY

2.1 MISSION – ENVISIONING IMPACT (MAXIMUM 250 WORDS)

Briefly describe the mission of the project, i.e. the main aims and objectives.

2.2 STRUCTURE – ORGANIZING IMPACT (MAXIMUM 250 WORDS)

Briefly describe the structure and organization of the project. Describe who the research and practice partners are.

2.3 RESEARCH – ENABLING IMPACT (MAXIMUM 500 WORDS)

Briefly describe the research that led to the impact. Provide details of what research was undertaken, when, and by whom. Describe what is unique about the research and why it is important. References to specific research outputs that embody the research described in this section, and evidence of its quality, should be provided in section 3.

¹ Economic and societal impact is the demonstrable contribution that excellent research makes to society and the economy, and its benefits to individuals, organizations and/or nations.

² Engagement is the interaction between researchers and research end-users outside of academia, for the mutually beneficial transfer of knowledge, technologies, methods or resources.

2.4 PATHWAY TO IMPACT – ACHIEVING IMPACT (MAXIMUM 750 WORDS)

Provide a narrative that clearly outlines the research impact. The narrative should explain how the associated research made a distinct and material contribution to the impact.

It should explain the nature and extent of the impact:

- who or what has benefitted from the results of the research (this should identify relevant research end-users, or beneficiaries from industry, the community, government, wider public etc.)
- the nature or type of impact and how the research made a societal, economic, and/or public policy and service impact
- the extent of the impact (with specific references to appropriate evidence, such as cost-benefit-analysis, quantity of those affected, reported benefits etc.)
- the dates and time period in which the impact occurred.

Provide a clear explanation of the process or means through which the research led to, underpinned or made a contribution to the impact (for example, how it was disseminated, how it came to influence users or beneficiaries, or how it came to be exploited, taken up or applied).

Provide a clear narrative of the engagement with parties, outside of academia, for the mutual benefit of the researchers and research end-users:

- the purpose of engagement, describing what the institution was trying to achieve through the engagement
- the type of the engagement activities
- the targeted parties of the engagement activities
- the duration and extent of the engagement activities

2.5 LEARNINGS – REFLECTING IMPACT (MAXIMUM 500 WORDS)

Provide based on your experience a critical reflection of possibilities, limits and novel methods to achieve economic and societal impact. Briefly describe as well adverse effects and unexpected problems related the pathway of impact.

Briefly describe how evidence for impact has been captured and how the OIS and engagement activities have been assessed. What types of indicators have been used to measure the OIS and engagement efforts as well as the derived impact?

3. SOURCES

Provide references to key outputs from the research described including:

- Author(s)
- Title

- Year of publication
- Type of output
- Access details (for example, a DOI or URL)

List sources to corroborate the key claims made in the Impact and Engagement Study. Sources provided should not be a substitute for providing clear evidence of impact.

If possible, provide relevant images linked to impact and engagement activities of the Ludwig Boltzmann Institute and the societal challenges addressed.

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